

FESTIVALS AND POVERTY ALLEVIATION IN THE PASSOVER NARRATIVES, THE NIGER DELTA EXPERIENCE

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Abstract

Generally speaking, festivals are periods when celebrants sit back to count their blessings. They also use that period to interact with one another; caring and sharing. This study looks at festival as an instrument of poverty alleviation. It attempts a comparative analysis of the Passover Feast in Exodus 12 and some festivals in Niger Delta. It notes that festivals are celebrated to mark a phase in a peoples' history; as a way of political liberation or cultural rejuvenation. The study underlines the fact that poverty may be structurally or environmentally imposed and to eliminate this, festival serves as an indispensable tool. The paper adopts the comparative approach in analysis and concludes that a people can shake themselves away from poverty when they poll their resources together in celebration.

Key word: Festival, poverty alleviation, Passover narratives

Introduction

Generally speaking, festivals are periods when a people sit back to count their blessings. Aware of the fact that humans desire order in the socio-religious sphere, rituals help to mend the relationship between the visible and invisible world. During festivals, broken fences in the socio-religious sphere are mended to restore order.

Scholars have tried to define the term festival. For instance, Ejizu (2007) looks at festival as any special occasion, observance or celebration which may be religious or secular in nature and generally marked by merry making, performance of music and the like. Modum (1978) points out its role from a typical African setting. He observes that the social and moral life in African societies is organized around festival manifestations which fulfils the function of social and moral control as well as provides entertainment and diversion. Webster Encyclopedia Dictionary defines festival as a time of celebration marked by special

observances, a periodic season or programme of cultural event or entertainment. The Oxford Advance Learners Dictionary holds that festivals refer to a series of public event connected with a particular activity or idea.

The definitions above present festival as a period of celebration and merry making, it is instituted to mark different occasion or stages in human circle. Organizers of festivals have something at the back of their mind. Ayinelechi (2013) contends that people celebrate one form of festival or the other to mark their independence or as a mark of reverence to the arch divinities for bountiful harvest, long life and prosperity. According to Okafor and Emeka (2008) "festivals and ceremonies constitute a principle of traditional education."

Though, some scholars argue that festivals lead to heavy indebtedness on the part of organizers; some also argue that it only brings about momentary poverty alleviation. This notwithstanding, the fun fare, spirit of caring and

sharing and elaborate spiritual and material preparation associated with festivals, presents it as avenue for poverty alleviation. The Passover narratives in Exodus 12:1-51 remain a good example of festival for poverty alleviation. Hence, this work highlights the comparative objective and effect of the Passover and some festivals in the Niger Delta of Nigeria as instruments of communal living, removal of class distinction, merriment and at the same time, stimulates economic prosperity as well as enhances social solidarity among the celebrants. Therefore, the argument that organizing festivals leads to waste of resources or momentary gain does not hold water as one must spend money to get money, the expenses during the period of preparation in this case can be seen as investment, more so, festivals bring about the revival and continuity of our cultural festivals that are at the verge of extinction due to modernization. We cannot also undermine the place of festival as a catalyst for the ingenious skills it provides to those in the arts and craft as they have to think outside the box to create art works that will be attractive to the people. That is why this paper holds the view that if the high spirit of preparation for festival is sustained it can generate fund, employment, etc. thereby reducing the spate of poverty and unemployment in the region.

The paper adopts the comparative analysis approach in the discussion. The paper opines that festivals no doubt leads to poverty alleviation.

Theoretical Framework

Sociologists like Scheller and Rank (2015) try to establish the root causes of poverty. These scholars see poverty as a very complex social problem with many variants. In a general sense, poverty may simply be seen as the lack of basic necessities. These include food, shelter, health care, clothing and safety. These scholars suggest that “poverty is created by the transmission over a generation by a set of belief, values and skills that are socially generated but individually held”. In the same vein, poverty could be traced to individual deficiencies and social phenomenon. Compelling individuals to abandon their culture and forcibly embrace another was also capable of inducing poverty as they will be struggling between the culture of their birth and the new.

Further, it is argued that regional and geographical concentration of people could result to poverty. Political and structural inequalities could be other contributory

factors. In a society of class distinction, structural inequality is bound to result to material poverty.

The Passover and Poverty Alleviation

In Exodus 12:1-51 God instituted the Passover for the Israelites to mark the commencement of a new era in their history. This was to mark the beginning of liberation from oppression, slavery, sufferings, poverty and all manner of ills. To show this, God commanded that the Passover be marked by the consumption of sumptuous meals of a lamb by every family. Hence, even families that ordinarily would not have had enough food to eat will be provided for by those who have more than enough to eat, nobody was left out in the eating and celebration, the period then became a time when everyone had enough food to eat. In the command of how to celebrate the liberty from slavery and oppression God warned them not to be lazy but be hard working by properly killing the lamb and roasting it with fire as against eating it raw. God warned them against wastage. He urged them to share with the poor in their midst.

This could be likened to festivals performed in the Niger Delta region as festivals in the region always creates a platform for sharing with those who do not have. Apart from sharing, it creates opportunity for economic generation as people use festival periods to do brisk businesses. This is because during period of festivals visitors will want to buy different items from their host communities, in fact during festivals in the Niger Delta ad-hoc markets are always created due to the influx of people into the community and increase in the sale of local goods.

Cultural Festivals in the Niger Delta

Owogbo Festival of Andoni

Owogbo festival is peculiar to the people of Ikuru town among the Andoni people. According to Julia Finomo, the festival takes place in January of every odd numbered year for instance 2003, 2005, etc. this festival showcases different types of masquerade most of which are aquatic in nature and these sea animals like hippopotamus (*otobo*) shark (*ofuruma*) tilapia (*ikop*) barracuda (*adot*) etc. There are few others which are not aquatic in nature like the *mkpi* (He-Goat) *Eniin* (Elephant) *Inigifuro* (Python) *Ikwut* (tortoise) and *Uji-akon* (War-Canoe). These masquerades are displayed in units known as *Okwa*; The *Okwa* is organized according to lineages and the celebration and masquerade exhibition spans within the period of fourteen days. New masquerades are made to

replace old and spoilt ones. As the festival continue with different masquerade displayed on different days. A day is devoted to the display of different kinds of fishes. This is done to show the children how the different fishes behave in water. As indicative of their aquatic environment the masquerade climaxes with the *Egbelegbe* masquerade. Within this period of fourteen days of celebration visitors and friends troop into the town, some lodge in hotels while some stay with their relatives. Thus, as a result of the influx of the people there is always the increase of buying and selling thereby stimulating the economy of the rural dwellers. The village is also kept very clean in preparation to receive guest from different parts of the town. The masquerade bearers abstain from sexual intercourse. Finomo (2005),

Owumangi Festival of Okrika

The *owumagi* festival was observed during the time of new corn. All able-bodied boys and young men in the island could partake in this festival at will. During the season, all young men and boys who could cope came out to the market square in the afternoon, each holding a deer horn or something else of value, a small body of people was responsible for organizing the show, which lasted for days and weeks in the season. A swift runner was always chosen and given two poles called *Okoloba*, each of about three feet long made out of the raffia palm branch.

With one of these in each hand, he chased them, and pressed to catch those running round and luring him to chase them, and pressed to catch him. If he succeeds, the person caught paid a fixed sum of money to redeem his horn or whatever he held in hand, which must be seized from him by the organizers as soon as he was caught. It is always a great shame to be caught at the view of girls, women and men spectators, anybody so chased must try to be at his best in running not to be caught (Opuogulaya, 1975).

Abua Cultural Festivals and Tourism Product

Eyaal Abuan

Eyaal Abuan is a time the people of Abua mark the beginning of a new year and the cleansing of the entire Abua land of sickness and diseases, poverty, prayers offered against flood, evil spirit, premature death and miscarriages, infertility of land and women barrenness. The period is also used for feasting and display of cultural plays, like masquerades, dancing, wrestling etc. The *Eyaal Abuan* is celebrated between March and April of every year. It is always on the 13th Calendar month

judging from the setting of the new moon or ebbing tide of the river. It is customary for an Abua person to predict the setting of the new moon through the ebb-flow of the sea water. The season is also the entrance to the raining season called "*Ogbo Unu*" meaning the middle of the raining season. Prior to this time people who reside in farming/fishing settlements '*araghanan*' will travel home to meet with relations, exchange gifts, repair thatch house, do wrestling, (*enuk*) masquerade (*arughu*) and carry out a Passover night (*Ogun-ekaraph*). This act signifies the entrance to a new year, hence, the need to cleanse the land of all manner of evil that may befall the land including flooding. During the night of Passover the *Odah Abuan* (King of Abua) takes the lead with his council of chiefs and the traditional priest of the land. While the cleansing is going on at Abua central, (the seat of the king) all other chiefs of other Abua villages are simultaneously carrying out the same cleansing ceremony the same time at midnight. At this time of the night nobody is expected to be seen outside as there is expected to be total darkness all over the village.

According to Obudu (oral source), the eve of the festival is always frightening because it is believed that the ancestors are part of the ceremony. Women and children are not allowed to step outside at night, no fishing and no farming during this period; as people are expected to have worked very hard in preparation for the festival. After the night of '*ekarap*' it becomes celebration all the way, different types of native food like plantain portages, fresh fish pepper soup, pounded yam, *onunu* etc, is being cooked and served among relations and guests.

During the *Eyaal* festival several masquerade and dances are displayed including traditional wrestling. The ceremonies last for four days with special prayers made by the king in conjunction with the village priest who presents different sacrifices to the gods of the land, (Lawrence-Hart G. 2012).

The Tin-Oge Festival of Ayama

Among the Anyama people of Southern Ijaw, "Tin-Oge" festival is a blend of tradition and economic principles. This festival spans over a period of seven days. Each of the days has different activities which space will not allow us to discuss here in detail.

Originally, this was an ancient festival to celebrate the protective powers of *Aguma* deity. In recent time, the *Tin-Oge* festival is to mark the day the Nigerian troop entered

the community and nobody died during the Nigerian civil war; Gbeinbo (2013). Many activities take place during this festival. The festival stretches into seven days. It starts on the *Akiebai* (the first day of the week) one of the unique features of the festival is the exchange of gifts to mark the commencement of the festival.

A lot of preparation goes into the celebration of this festival. This ranges from cleaning the community, gathering of food to setting up of various committees to take care of different aspects of the ceremony. As part of the activities, sons-in-laws are required to present gifts of tin of palm oil, bunches of palm fruit, bags of palm kernel and jars of drink to their fathers-in-laws as a mark of capacity to maintain their daughters. In a similar manner, daughters-in-law send baskets of yam, basins of starch and water yam to their mothers-in-law to demonstrate that their sons are not doing badly.

Housewives prepare sumptuous meals to demonstrate the mood of the period. Starch, *fufu*, portage plantain are served with fresh fish pepper soup. At every compound, adult males assemble to eat and drink together. The youth after taking their meal, sing from one compound to the other and are welcomed with some monetary gifts.

Visitors are not left out, while the “*tin-oge*” festival lasts, visitors from far and near grace the ceremony. From the palace of the “*Amananowe*” to the home of subjects, guests are lavishly entertained. Other social activities like masquerading add colour to the event.

Comparative Analysis of the Passover Feast and the Niger Delta Festivals

As stated earlier, this paper makes a comparative analysis of the Passover feast in Exodus 12 and the various festivals in the Niger Delta. From the above narrative of the festivals in the Niger Delta, it is imperative to note that both festivals marks seasons of celebration bequeathed to the present generation by their forebears. We could also see that these festivals create avenues for preparation and provision of abundance of food both by the rich and poor thereby stimulating industry and commerce. Also evident, is the increase in the activities of communal life that creates a bond of unity among the people to the effect that equitable distribution of items for celebration is highly practiced. It creates a unique community which makes the “*haves*” and “*do-not-have*” celebrate without discrimination. More interesting, is the spirit of saving.

Just as the children of Israel preserved lambs without blemishes for the Passover feast, the Niger Deltans also work hard to save money and all manner of food items to serve their guests during festivals.

This paper believes that if the high spirit of hard work and preparation for festivals is sustained it will drastically reduce the level of poverty. Furthermore, if there are provisions for storage facility to preserve excess food to avoid waste it will be of great gain to the people. This is because in every festival there is always an overflow of food that is why God instructed the children of Israel to prepare their meals according their family strength and also take cognizance of those who do not have. Left-over must be properly burnt to avoid littering the environment; especially due to the fact that there were no preservatives/storage facilities in that era. However, in this modern era, storage facilities can be made available to make food/fruits available at a moderate price all year round. This we believe will provide job opportunities for those who will be employed to manage this storage facilities thereby reducing poverty among the people.

Finally, if the government can embark on revitalizing and investing on our festivals just as the Israelites heeded to the instruction of God to keep the Passover feast, the festivals will attract tourist and reduce poverty to the barest minimum in the region.

Conclusion

As a memorial and inheritance, the Passover is still celebrated in Israel. This is a replica of what is obtained in the Niger Delta as most of the festivals are bequeathed to the present generation by their forebears just like the Passover feast. Festivals in the region is also a time of joy and merriment, thus people work hard to prepare for festivals such that food is provided in abundance in every house hold during this period. It is difficult to notice those who are poor since everybody work assiduously in preparation for the festival. In the same vein, people are seen adorned with beautiful clothes with elegance as a reflection of the joyous mood associated with festivals.

Festivals bring an atmosphere of joy and excitement. In addressing poverty alleviation, it stimulate commerce as those who are into costume making will be patronized, photographers, transporters, hospitality, industry, etc, will all be empowered owing to the beehive of activity during festivals.

Recommendations

In view of the enormous role festivals play in alleviating poverty, the following suggestions may help to improve on it.

- i) Owing to the fact that festivals help to alleviate poverty, those festivals that seem to be dying away should be revived.
- ii) Governments at both state and federal levels should catalogue all festivals in the country to boost tourism development.
- iii) The profits made after festival sales should be re-invested for greater benefit.
- iv) The effort directed while preparing for festivals should be extended to other activities that contribute to poverty alleviation.
- v) Food processing/storage facilities should be provided to enable feasting communities preserve the excess food and other perishable materials gathered for the celebration of festivals.
- vi) The spirit of caring and sharing which characterizes all festivals should be extended to periods after the celebration.
- vii) People should not save or lend money only for the celebration. The habit of saving should also be applied for other purposes.
- viii) Similarly, the environmental cleanliness and hygiene which characterizes all festive seasons should be extended to periods outside the season.

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